

THE ROLES OF PORE DISTRIBUTION AND HIERARCHICAL STRUCTURE OF MARINE MUSSEL PLAQUE CORES

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ABSTRACT

The thread-plaque system of marine mussels demonstrates strong adhesion and high deformability, enabling it to stick to various wet surfaces. The plaque has a sandwich structure with a porous core enclosed by a dense cuticle layer. Although the microstructures of plaque cores have been reported, the impact of their unique porous structure on high deformability remains unclear. This study used scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to investigate the porous structure of mussel plaque cores. Two-dimensional (2D) porous representative volume elements (RVEs) with scaled distribution parameters were generated, and the calibrated phase-field modelling method was applied to analyse the effect of pore distribution and multi-scale porous structure on the failure mechanisms of porous RVEs. SEM analysis revealed that large-scale pores have a lognormal size distribution and a uniform spatial distribution. Simulations indicated that increasing the normalized mean radius value of the large-scale pore distribution statistically leads to a decrease in final failure strain, strength, and strain energy density, but cannot solely determine their values. The interaction between pores can result in two different failure modes under the same pore distribution: progressive failure mode and sudden failure mode. Additionally, the hierarchical structure of multi-scale porous RVEs can increase the final failure strain by 40–60% compared to single-scale porous RVEs by reducing stiffness, suggesting that the hierarchical structure could be another key factor contributing to high deformability. These findings enhance our understanding of how pore distribution and multi-scale porous structure in mussel plaque cores contribute to their high deformability and affect other mechanical properties, offering valuable insights for designing highly deformable composite materials in the future.

1 INTRODUCTION

The mussel byssus system, comprising protein threads and porous plaques (Fig. 1a–b), enables strong anchoring to diverse surfaces in harsh marine environments [1–7]. Notably, mussel plaques exhibit exceptional ductility, allowing significant deformation under tensile loads without failure (Fig. 1c), a property with promising implications for bioinspired material design. Despite extensive research into their adhesive performance [8–11], the underlying mechanisms contributing to their high ductility remain poorly understood.

Structurally, mussel plaques feature a porous core encased by a protective cuticle (Fig. 1b) [12]. The core contains randomly distributed nano- and micro-scale pores (75–100 nm to 1–3 μm in diameter; Fig. 1e) [12]. Prior studies suggest that modifying pore arrangement can enhance ductility [13]. Gockowski et al. (2020) proposed that increasing crack path tortuosity through tailored pore structures may account for this effect [14]. However, these studies largely

employed idealized, ordered pore geometries, differing from the natural pore architecture of mussel plaques [13,14]. As such, the role of the native, multi-scale porous structure in enhancing mechanical performance—particularly ductility—remains insufficiently explored.

This study aims to bridge that gap by investigating how pore distribution (Figs. 1d and f) and hierarchical porosity (Fig. 1e) affect the mechanical behavior of mussel plaques. Pore morphology was characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and two-dimensional porous representative volume elements (RVEs) were generated with scaled distribution parameters for both numerical and experimental analysis. A validated phase-field fracture model incorporating a Neo-Hookean hyperelastic material law was used to simulate the influence of pore structure on failure mechanisms. This work offers insights into the ductility mechanisms of mussel plaques and informs the design of bioinspired, highly deformable metamaterials.

Figure 1: (a) Mussel byssus system attached on a rock, (b) schematic diagram of the mussel plaque's microstructure, (c) large deformation of mussel plaque under tension, (d) the distribution of normalized x and y coordinates for large pore centres within the mussel plaque core, (e) the SEM photo showing the multi-scale porous structure of mussel plaque core and (f) the distribution of normalized radius for large pores within the mussel plaque core.

2. THE SEM CHARACTERISATION OF MUSSEL PLAQUE CORE

Two-dimensional (2D) SEM images have suggested that the pores within the plaque cores are of two different scales, ranging in diameter from 75-100 nm (small-scale pores) to 1-3 μm (large-scale pores) (Fig. 1d). The pore distribution of large-scale pores within those SEM photos was first examined. In order to ensure the representativeness of the large-scale pore distribution in these photos, a total of nine SEM photos from different plaques or different locations of the same plaque were analysed. The irregular large-scale pores were simplified as equivalent circular pores to obtain the pore distribution during the SEM image analysis. The longest axis

of the irregular large-scale pores was considered as the diameter of the equivalent circular pores. Meanwhile, the radii of large-scale pores and the coordinates of the pore centres were normalised by dividing the length of SEM image (l_s) edges for the distribution analysis.

Figure 2: Pore distribution analysis of mussel plaque SEM images.

3. THE GENERATION OF THE RVES FOR THE POROUS STRUCTURE

Two types of porous RVEs were generated for numerical study. The first RVE type investigates the effect of large-scale pores, while the second RVE type examines the impact of the multi-scale architecture of the mussel plaque core.

The first type RVE was generated by scaling the plaque pore sizes by a factor of 1000, transitioning from microns to millimetres. Two-dimensional (2D) square shaped porous RVEs were generated by using the scaled distribution parameters of the large-scale pores ($v_l=27\%$, $\mu_p^*=1.12\text{ mm}$ and $s_p^*=0.34\text{ mm}$). The dimensions of the RVEs are 30 x 30 mm, comprising solely large-scale pores with the remaining volume filled with solid material, see Fig.3.

The second type RVE representing multi-scale porous structures were generated via removing 2D elements in the FE models and connecting the nodes using truss elements of circular cross sections (i.e. coupled temperature-displacement truss element T2D2T) (Fig. 3). The radius of the truss elements was determined to ensure that the newly generated RVEs reflected the same overall porosity ($v = v_s + v_l = 32\%$) with the SEM image (Fig. 1e). Here, v_s represents the volume fraction of smaller pores.

Figure 3: The first type RVE (left) and the second type RVE (right)

4. ABAQUS IMPLEMENTATION AND EXPERIMENTAL CALIBRATION OF THE PHASE FIELD MODELLING METHOD

The phase field method was numerically implemented in ABAQUS, based on heat transfer analogy, using combined User subroutines UHYPER and HETVAL. The comparison of numerical modelling and experimental measurement is shown in Figs. 4 and 5.

Figure 4 : Schematic drawings of the porous samples for tensile testing

Figure 5: Comparison between the (a-c) numerical and experimental stress-strain curves and (d-f) fracture paths for three porous samples in tension.

5. RESULTS OF THE RVES ANALYSIS

Figure 6 shows the macroscopic stress-strain curve and crack propagation of Sample A, which had the highest values of $\Delta\varepsilon$, ε_{ff} , and φ among the 400 RVE results. Here, $\Delta\varepsilon$ denotes the difference between the initial and final failure strain, ε_{ff} the final failure strain and strength and the strength (σ_{max}). For comparison, the stress-strain curves and crack propagation of two additional samples, B and C, are also presented in Figure 6. It is noted that samples A, B and C have nearly identical normalised standard deviation (\bar{s}) and mean ($\bar{\mu}$) values for radius of pores, with a difference of only ± 0.001 .

Two different failure modes were identified from the stress-strain curves of the samples: progressive failure and sudden failure (Fig. 6A). For the progressive failure sample (Sample A), the $\Delta\varepsilon$ value was approximately 50% of the final failure strain. In contrast, the $\Delta\varepsilon$ value for the sudden failure sample (Sample C) was close to 0 (Fig. 6A). The final failure strain of the progressive failure sample (Sample A) was about 1.5 times that of the sudden failure sample (Sample C), but its strength was only approximately 85% of Sample C's strength (Fig. 6A). Interestingly, the strength of these samples decreased with increasing $\Delta\varepsilon$ (Fig. 6A), indicating that the high ductility of the plaques may have been achieved by sacrificing strength.

Figure 6: (A) The macroscopic stress-strain curves, and (B) crack paths of selected samples with different failure modes.

The normalised mean ($\bar{\mu}$) and standard deviation ($\bar{\sigma}$) of pore radius reflect the statistic characteristic of the pore distribution within the single-scale RVEs, raising the question of whether these two parameters have a dominant effect on mechanical behaviour. To address this, the simulation results for 400 samples were analysed to establish the functional relations between the initial and final failure strain ($\Delta\varepsilon$), final failure strain (ε_{ff}), strength (σ_{max}), and strain energy density (φ) and the normalized mean ($\bar{\mu}$) and standard deviation ($\bar{\sigma}$).

Figure 7: The 2D linear regression analysis between the normalised mean value standard $\bar{\mu}$ of the large-scale pore radius and (a) $\Delta\varepsilon$, (b) final failure strain (ε_{ff}), (c) strength (σ_{max}), and (d) strain energy density (φ).

The results of the linear regression demonstrate that the overall effects of the normalised standard deviation (\bar{s}) on $\Delta\varepsilon$, ε_{ff} , σ_{max} , and φ were statistically insignificant for the 400 samples. Conversely, the regression analysis indicates that an increase in the normalised mean radius ($\bar{\mu}$) led to an overall decrease in strength (σ_{max}), strain energy density (φ), and final failure strain (ε_{ff}), respectively (Figs. 7b, c and d). While a different overall trend was observed for $\Delta\varepsilon$: as $\bar{\mu}$ increased, the value of $\Delta\varepsilon$ exhibited a slight increase (Figure 7a).

It is important to note that linear regression analysis only illustrates the overall trend of the effect of the normalised mean ($\bar{\mu}$) and standard deviation (\bar{s}) on these parameters and cannot capture the high dispersion of the results (Figure 7). It can be seen from Figure 7 that the same $\bar{\mu}$ can always return scattered $\Delta\varepsilon$, ε_{ff} , σ_{max} , or φ values. This may suggest that, while the normalised mean value ($\bar{\mu}$) of pore radius can influence the ductility or other macroscopic material properties of the single-scale RVE, it might not be the sole determining factor. Other factors such as the distance between pores or the multi-scale structure could also play an important role.

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